

Analysis of battery module cooler for electric vehicles

Juraj Paulech^{1, a)}, Martin Baťa¹

Author Affiliations

¹*Department of Applied Mechanics and Mechatronics, Institute of Automotive Mechatronics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Ilkovičova 3, 812 19 Bratislava, Slovak Republic.*

Author Emails

^{a)} *Corresponding author: juraj.paulech@stuba.sk*

Abstract. The paper presents Computation Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation of cooler system for small Li-Ion battery module suitable for electromobile's traction battery. The results from simulation show the difference in cooling effect for individual cells in terms of their different operation temperature. This difference in cells' temperature should be the input for further State of Charge (SOC) and State of Health (SOH) calculation and evaluation of battery module.

INTRODUCTION

Traction electric battery is the most expensive, heaviest, and crucial part of a battery electric vehicle (BEV). Omitting types of range extenders for BEV, the traction battery is the only storage of traction energy for operation of the vehicle. Therefore, it is inevitable to maintain its long operational life and safety – in the ideal case during the entire considered life of the vehicle.

The traction battery consists of individual modules that include a selected number of cells, electrically conductive connections, battery management system, cooling system and package. During the discharge of individual cells while driving, but especially when charging the traction battery on a fast charger, significant Joule heat is generated in the cells caused by the flow of electric current through the internal electrical resistance of the cells. In the absence of a cooling system, this heat would cause overheating of the cells in the battery pack, which would lead to a significant decrease in the life of the traction battery due to the irreversible chemical degradation of the cell materials. Moreover, in case of critical overheating, the traction battery could also catch fire, especially with the currently most used Li-Ion cell technology, where the chemistry of these cells contains both a source of fuel and an oxidizer for the combustion process. Therefore, mainly the water-cooled systems are used for modern battery electric vehicles [1]. These systems are often modelled using CFD approach [2].

This article describes the simulation of cooling of small battery module that consists of 15 Li-Ion cells, cell holders and water cooler with metal ribs. The design of the cooler is deliberately chosen so that, with the same generated heat power in the cells, it ensures their uneven cooling, and thus due to the different operating temperatures of the individual cells, their unequal State of Health (SOH) and State of Charge (SOC) is achieved, which will be the subject of a subsequent scientific investigations, which, however, will not be described in this article.

DESCRIPTION OF THE CFD MODEL

Fig. 1 shows the geometry and internal view into the small battery module model. The cells are standard cylindrical 18 650 Li-Ion cells (diameter 18 mm, length 65 mm). Overall dimensions of the model are 113 × 80 × 63 mm. Water cooler is made of copper with thermal conductivity of 401 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹, cell holders are plastic (1 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹), cells are considered as homogenous material with thermal conductivity of 237 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹. Electric buses for serial and parallel cell connection are also copper.

FIGURE 1. Geometric model (top) and internal view into the model (bottom) for small battery module

Fig. 2 shows mesh for Finite Volume Method (FVM), that is the numerical method typically used for fluid flow computer analyses. The model was simulated using ANSYS CFX [3] software that is incorporated in ANSYS Workbench [4] environment.

The CFD analysis in ANSYS CFX calculates heat transfer through solid and fluid domains and calculates fluid (water, in this case) flow in channels of metal cooler, see Fig. 3. The heat transfer is based on boundary conditions that are:

- Joule heat power in overall volume of each cell is 10 W,
- water mass flow in each channel is 0.01 kg/s with inlet temperature of 25°C,
- water outlet from the model is described using 0 Pa pressure condition,
- for simplification and for the worst-case scenario, no external air convection is considered.

Static fluid flow analysis with thermal energy calculation is considered. Joule heat power in cells is relatively high and represents critically high battery charging.

FIGURE 2. FVM mesh of the model – full view (top left), internal view (top right), detail for water domain (bottom left), cross-section of the mesh (bottom right)

FIGURE 3. Boundary conditions for water flow in ANSYS CFX

CFD ANALYSIS

The model was calculated using iterative ANSYS CFX solver. Results of the converged steady-state solution are shown in Fig. 4 where temperature distribution in cells, cooler's metal ribs and cooler's channels filled with water is presented. Temperature difference between individual cells is high, while rise of temperature of water is small, see Fig. 5. Such ineffective cooler provides good input for further computational and laboratory analyses of SOH and SOC of cells that operate under different temperature conditions in time.

FIGURE 4. Temperature distribution in cells, cooler and water for CFD analysis

FIGURE 5. Temperature distribution in water using streamline visualization

CONCLUSIONS

The paper presented CFD thermal analysis of small battery module suitable for traction batteries in electric vehicles. Cooling possibilities of water cooler with metallic ribs was described. Uneven temperature distribution in individual cells under high thermal loading conditions due to fast charging was presented. This thermal state was required and expected. Such differences in temperature during operation of the cells lead to changes in State of Health and State of Charge of the individual cells with impact to their lifetime, lifetime of the battery module and even the overall battery pack. Evaluation of SOH and SOC will be the topic for further scientific investigation and experiments. Computer simulation was used because of the time benefit in comparison to an experiment and also because of the need to avoid cells damage or degradation in the real experiment.

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